

Proyecto **PID2020-118041GB-I00** financiado
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**UNIVERSIDAD
DE GRANADA**

User Guide of MonitorEO-EarthCul - Google Earth Engine App EarthCul PID2020-118041GB-I00

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1. Introduction

MonitorEO-EarthCul is a browser-based geospatial analysis platform developed using **Google Earth Engine Apps**. It is designed to provide structured access to and visualization of both **input variables** and **model outputs** generated within the framework of the **EarthCul project** (PID2020-118041GB-I00).

The platform focuses on the **characterization and monitoring of ecosystem services** in mountain National Parks across Spain and Portugal. It allows users to explore and interpret a wide range of **satellite-derived indicators**, spatial models, and cartographic products. These outputs support both **scientific research** and **environmental decision-making** by offering tools for spatial and temporal analysis.

This user manual serves as a complete guide to using MonitorEO-EarthCul. It covers the platform's main features, interface navigation, parameter configuration (e.g., ecosystem service type, modeling scope, temporal filters), and map layer visualization. The guide also explains the structure of inputs and outputs, and how users can interact with multiple spatial layers simultaneously.

The platform has been developed by the **University of Granada** and funded by the **Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation**.

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2. Graphical User Interface (GUI)

The **MonitorEO-EarthCul interface (Figure 1)** is a user-friendly, browser-based application built on Google Earth Engine Apps, designed to facilitate the spatial and temporal exploration of ecosystem service indicators derived from satellite imagery. The interface is tailored to support scientific research, spatial modeling, and decision-making in protected mountain areas.

Figure 1. MonitorEO-EarthCul interface

2.1. Interface Components

The interface consists of two main panels:

- **Left Control Panel**

This vertical panel allows users to configure map visualizations by selecting language, study area (ROI), dates or time period, ecosystem service category, variable source type, modeling scope (if applicable) and thematic filters (category, group, subcategory). Once parameters are set, the **Show Layer** button activates the rendering of the selected layer.

All configuration options are explained in detail in later sections of this manual.

- **Map Display Area**

Powered by Google Maps and Google Earth Engine:

- Displays the satellite imagery and selected cartographic outputs.
- Interactive features include zoom, pan, layer switching (Map/Satellite), and full-screen view.
- Map legend and metadata are dynamically updated based on the active selection.

2.2. Key Functionalities

- **Dynamic Map Rendering:** Selected data layers are loaded in real time based on user-defined parameters.
- **Scalability:** Supports high-resolution spatial layers and time-series data across multiple regions.
- **Transparency and Layer Control:** Visual adjustment tools are provided for better interpretation of overlapping data.
- **Metadata Access:** Legends, units, and data sources are automatically displayed for each variable.

2.3. Intended Use

This GUI has been designed to:

- Provide researchers, environmental managers, and policy makers with access to spatial information related to **ecosystem services**.
- Enable comparative analysis across parks and time periods.
- Serve as a decision-support tool for conservation planning and ecosystem service evaluation.

3. Languages

Select the interface language (Figure 2). The following options are available:

- **en** English
- **es** Spanish

Figure 2. Select language.

4. Study area

Available ROIs – EarthCul Socio-Economic Influence Areas

Users can define the **Region of Interest (ROI)** by selecting from the predefined spatial extents associated with the EarthCul project (Figure 3). These ROIs correspond to the **socio-economic influence zones of mountain National Parks in Spain and Portugal**.

The following National Parks are currently available as ROI options within the application:

- Aigüestortes i Estany de Sant Maurici
- Ordesa y Monte Perdido
- Peneda-Gerês (Portugal)
- Picos de Europa
- Guadarrama

- Sierra de las Nieves
- Sierra Nevada
- Teide

Figure 3. ROI selection.

5. Dates

This control enables the temporal filtering of geospatial datasets based on the selected time range (Figure 4). At present, the interface provides access to **current-condition models**, representing ecosystem service indicators derived from recent satellite observations.

Future versions of the platform will incorporate **climate change scenarios**, allowing users to visualize and analyze **short-term and long-term predictive projections** derived from spatial modeling and scenario-based projections.

Figure 4. Dates selection.

6. Ecosystem service category

This dropdown menu allows users to define the thematic focus of the analysis by selecting the **category of ecosystem service** to be visualized or modeled (Figure 5). The available categories are derived from socio-cultural and land-use typologies relevant to ecosystem service assessment in protected mountainous areas.

Depending on the selected **National Park** and the availability of spatial data, the following categories may be available:

- **Cultural** – Services related to symbolic values, local identity, traditions, or heritage.
- **Fauna and Flora** – Perception and appreciation of biodiversity (e.g., wildlife watching, endemic species).
- **Gastronomy** – Links between local food traditions.
- **Nature Landscape** – Aesthetic and scenic qualities of natural environments.
- **Recreational** – Opportunities for leisure activities.
- **Religious** – Cultural and spiritual significance of places (e.g., pilgrimage routes, sacred sites).

- **Rural Tourism** – Tourism experiences associated with rural lifestyles and traditional practices.
- **Sports** – Outdoor or nature sports including skiing, mountain biking, or trail running.
- **Sun and Beach** – Recreational and aesthetic services in coastal or semi-coastal areas.
- **Urban** – Cultural and recreational services in urban-adjacent natural settings.

The selected category filters the **available indicators and spatial layers**, tailoring the data visualization to reflect only the ecosystem service components relevant to that theme. This step is essential for ensuring interpretability and thematic coherence of the output maps.

Figure 5. Ecosystem Services categories.

7. Variable source

This control allows users to specify the **type of variable** to be visualized within the selected spatial and thematic context (Figure 6). The variable selection determines the nature of the dataset displayed on the map and is essential for understanding the modeling structure and interpretation of results.

Two main variable types are available:

- **Input Variable Models:**
These are the baseline or explanatory variables used as inputs in the ecosystem service models. They include environmental, socio-economic, or spatial attributes

that influence service provision. Examples include: Accessibility (public transport, parking distance...), Climate (e.g. weather and climate), Ecosystem structure (e.g. Biodiversity), Tourism and Culture (accommodation), Flickr and Twitter presences.

- **Output Variable Models – Ecosystem Service Habitat Suitability:**

These represent the results or predicted outputs of modeling processes, expressed as spatial suitability maps. They estimate the potential distribution or intensity of a cultural ecosystem service (e.g., recreation, aesthetic value) based on input variables and statistical or rule-based modeling approaches.

Selecting the appropriate variable type is critical for aligning the visualization with the intended analytical objective—whether exploring influencing factors (inputs) or assessing ecosystem service potential (outputs).

Figure 6. Selection of inputs or outputs models variables.

8. Modeling Scope

This setting allows users to define the modeling configuration used to generate the selected output variable. It is only applicable when “Output Variable Models” are selected under the *Variable* field.

Available options may include:

- **Model per park:** Executes or visualizes models that have been calibrated individually for each protected area.

- **General model:** Uses a unified model structure applied consistently across all parks, allowing for inter-site comparison under standardized conditions.

This control affects how spatial predictions are generated and interpreted, particularly in terms of local adaptation versus generalization.

9. Input model variables

When the user selects **Input model variables** under the *Variable Source Type* field, a structured selection process is enabled to define the specific spatial input layer to be visualized or used in modeling. The following fields become active:

- **Thematic Group:**
Defines the general domain or topic of the input data (e.g., Accessibility, Land Use...).
- **Subcategory:**
Refines the selected thematic group into more specific dimensions (e.g., distance to roads, trail density, slope class).
- **Input Layer:**
Refers to the specific geospatial dataset or raster layer to be used. This is the final selection that determines what will be rendered on the map.

These fields are dynamically linked, meaning the options available in each depend on the previous selection. Input variables serve as the foundational layers for modeling ecosystem services and understanding spatial drivers of service distribution.

10. Show Layers

This button executes the rendering of the selected spatial data layer on the map interface, based on the current parameter configuration. It triggers data loading and visualization processes, allowing users to view the thematic content associated with their selections.

11. Map Layers Visualization and Control

Once a layer is loaded using the **Show Layer** button, it is displayed on the interactive map interface. Users can **load multiple layers simultaneously**, which allows for comparative analysis or multi-variable exploration (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Map layers visualization and control.

The interface includes **layer control functionalities**, which enable users to:

- **Toggle visibility:** Activate or deactivate individual layers without removing them.
- **Adjust transparency:** Modify the opacity of each layer to better visualize overlapping information or base maps.
- **Stack multiple layers:** Visualize thematic relationships by overlaying several datasets.

This functionality enhances the flexibility and interpretability of spatial analyses performed through the platform.